

Studies on the Behaviour of Uni-bivalent Salt in Aqueous Solution. Part II. Sodium Oxalate and Determination of Standard Electrode Potential of

$$\text{Ag} \mid \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$$

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The study of the cells of the type:

(a) $\text{Ag} \mid \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \parallel \text{Satd. KCl} \parallel \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 indicates that sodium oxalate is completely dissociated in the concentration range of 0.0083 to 0.0395 moles/litre.

The study of cells:

(b) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{NaCl} \parallel \text{Satd. KCl} \parallel \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 $4C \qquad \qquad \qquad C$

(c) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{NaCl} \mid \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 $4C \qquad \qquad \qquad C$

shows that the standard electrode potential of $\text{Ag} \mid \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ is -0.4591 volt.

The following types of cells:

(a) $\text{Ag} \mid \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \parallel \text{Satd. KCl} \parallel \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 $C_1 \qquad \qquad \qquad C_2$

(b) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{NaCl} \parallel \text{Satd. KCl} \parallel \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 $4C \qquad \qquad \qquad C$

(c) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{NaCl} \mid \text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \mid \text{Ag}$
 $4C \qquad \qquad \qquad C$

were studied in order to know the extent of dissociation of sodium oxalate and to find out the standard electrode potential (E_0) for the half-cell $\text{Ag} \mid \text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Silver oxalate used was prepared by the action of silver nitrate on sodium oxalate and was recrystallised thrice from ammonia. Sodium oxalate and sodium chloride solutions were prepared from G. R. quality salts in double distilled water. To avoid the growth of fungus and subsequent decomposition sodium oxalate solution was not kept for more than 24 hours.

Silver was deposited on the platinum as described by Jena and Prasad (this *Journal* 1960, 37, 634) by thermal decomposition of silver oxalate on platinum. Some silver oxalate was spread on the silver-coated platinum wire and the vessels were then filled with required sodium oxalate solution, which was drained off three times to wash the silver oxalate.

The technique of setting the cells was as described in the earlier papers (*loc. cit.*) The E. M. F. values of the cells of the type (a), (b), and (c) are shown in column 3 of Table I and columns 3 and 4 of Table II.

TABLE I

Cell used: type (a).

Conc. of $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ (gm moles/litr.)		E. M. F. of cell (a).	E. M. F. calc. from equation (1).	Diff.
C_1 .	C_2 .			
0.0210	0.0136	4.8mv	4.7mv	0.1mv
0.0299	0.0150	6.4	6.0	0.4
0.0278	0.0083	10.5	11.9	0.4
0.0395	0.0209	4.8	4.9	0.1

TABLE II

Cells used: type (b) and (c).

Conc. (gm moles/litre).		E. M. f. of cell (b).	E.M.F. of Cell (c)	Diff.
$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	NaCl .			
0.010	0.04	0.1728 volt	0.1638 volt	0.90mv
0.015	0.06	0.1792	0.1706	0.86
0.020	0.08	0.1843	0.1755	0.88
0.025	0.10	0.1869	0.1788	0.81
0.030	0.12	0.1906	0.1820	0.86
Average				0.86

TABLE III

Conc. (gm. moles/litre)		E.M.F. of cell (b)	E.M.F. Calc. for half-cells.	
$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	NaCl		Chloride half-cell. ($-E_{\text{Cl}}$)	Oxalate half-cell. $-E_{\text{ox}}$
0.005	0.02	0.1630 volt	0.3733 volt	0.5363 volt
0.010	0.04	0.1728	0.3565	0.5293
0.015	0.06	0.1792	0.3462	0.5254
0.020	0.08	0.1843	0.3393	0.5236
0.025	0.10	0.1869	0.3338	0.5207
0.030	0.12	0.1906	0.3294	0.5200

DISCUSSION

Assuming the elimination of liquid junction potential (l. j. p.) by the salt bridge, the E. M. F. of the cells of type (a) will be given by the equation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{C_1 f_1}{C_2 f_2} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Where C and f are the concentration and activity coefficients of oxalate ion in the solution. Assuming complete dissociation of sodium oxalate and assuming that the activity coefficient of the oxalate ion is the same as that of the sulphate ion at the same concentration, the E. M. F's. of the cells have been calculated and are recorded in column 4 of Table I. Comparison with experimental values (column 3) shows good agreement.

Assuming elimination of l. j. p. by saturated KCl, the E. M. F. E' of cell (b) would be given by the relation,

$$E' = E_{\text{Cl}} - E_{\text{ox}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Where E_{Cl} and E_{Ox} are the potentials of the two half elements of the cell. To ascertain the elimination of l. j. p. or otherwise, cell (c) was studied. The E.M.F, E'' , of cell (c), is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} E'' &= E_{Cl} - E_{Ox} + E_j \\ &= E' + E_j \end{aligned} \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

where E_j is the liquid junction potential developed at the junction of sodium oxalate and sodium chloride. If the bridge used in cells of the type 'b' eliminates liquid junction potential, then the difference of E.M.F. of cells of the types 'b' and 'c' should be equal to E_j . The value of E_j was calculated from the mobility values of sodium, chloride and oxalate ions, which are 61.1, 89.2, 87.7 respectively, (Glasstone, *Electrochemistry of Solutions*, p. 72), and Henderson's equation which reduces to the following form for the solution used.

$$E_j = \frac{RT}{F} \frac{2U_{Na^+} - 4V_{Cl^-} + V_{\frac{1}{2}C_2O_4^{2-}}}{4V_{Cl^-} - 2V_{\frac{1}{2}C_2O_4^{2-}} + 2U_{Na^+}} \log_e \frac{2U_{Na^+} + 2V_{Cl^-}}{U_{Na^+} + V_{\frac{1}{2}C_2O_4^{2-}}} \quad (4)$$

The value of E_j calculated comes out to be -0.0090 volt for all cells of the type (c). On an average the value of E_j calculated agrees with those obtained from difference ($E'' - E'$) to within 0.4 mv (Table II, last column), thereby showing that liquid junction potential is effectively eliminated by the salt bridge in the cells of the type 'b'.

The E. M.F. E_{Cl} , of chloride half-cell $Hg | Hg_2Cl_2, NaCl$, calculated as in previous papers is given in column 4 of Table III. Electrode potential (E_{Ox}) of oxalate half-cells, $Ag | Ag_2C_2O_4, Na_2C_2O_4$ calculated from equation (2) is given in column 5 in Table III. The E. M.F. of oxalate half-cell is given by the following equation:

$$E_{Ox} = E^{\circ}_{Ox} + \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e c.f.^{2-} \quad (5)$$

The substitution of the value of activity coefficients from Debye-Hückel equation reduces equation (5) to the form:

$$E_{Ox} - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e [C_2O_4^{2-}] + \frac{4.606RT}{F} A\sqrt{\mu} = E^{\circ}_{Ox} + B\mu$$

where, 'A' is the usual constant having the value 0.516 (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2179). The left hand side of this equation is plotted against ionic strength and from the plot the value of E°_{Ox} is found to be -0.4591 . This value may have an error of ± 0.5 mv. The standard electrode potential, reported earlier by Ferrell *et al* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948 70, 3812) is -0.4624 . There are two uncertainties in their work. They have assumed a value for dissociation constant of oxalic acid which may not be very accurate and they have determined the value of E°_{Ox} by extrapolating the results of two readings only, to zero ionic strength. We presume that our value is more correct.

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